

FRIEDEL-CRAFTS' REACTION INVOLVING UNSATURATED KETONES AND ESTERS. PART V. ALKYLATION OF CUMENE AND *p*-CYMENE WITH ETHYL ALLYLACETATE AND ALLYLACETONE

BY S. M. MUKHERJI, O. P. VIG, N. K. MAHESWARY AND SARJIT SINGH SANDHU

The Friedel-Crafts alkylation of cumene and *p*-cymene with ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone leads respectively to the *p*-oriented products and *p*-cymyl-2 derivatives. These products prove to be useful intermediates in the elegant synthesis of a variety of naphthalene derivatives.

In view of our experience with toluene, which on the Friedel-Crafts alkylation with ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone afforded the *meta*-oriented products (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 1499), it was reasonably expected that cumene on similar treatment with ethyl allylacetate would give rise to ethyl 4-(*m*-cumyl)-valerate, which would form an elegant pathway to eudalene, the well-known naphthalene derivative obtained on dehydrogenation of sesquiterpenes of eudesmol group (Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 345, 369, 923). However, our expectation was not realised, because when cumene and ethyl allylacetate were subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction at 0°-5°, the product obtained in 66% yield was found to be the *para*-isomer (I). This ester was hydrolysed in the usual way to the corresponding acid (II), which on cyclisation by Johnson's inverse technique (Johnson and Glenn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1092) furnished the ketone (III), properties of which as well as those of its derivatives corresponded very closely with those of 4-methyl-7-isopropyl-1-tetralone, obtained by Ruzicka *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, **16**, 269) by a longer route.

That the product (I) was the *para*-isomer was further proved by alkaline permanganate oxidation of the acid (II) to the exclusive oxidation product, terephthalic acid, identified as its *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative. No trace of phthalic or isophthalic acid could be detected. The *para*-orientation in the case of cumene is rather intriguing when contrasted with the *meta*-orientation with toluene. It is, however, evident that although the alkylating carbonium ion is the same, the alkyl group (*isopropyl*) already present in the case of cumene is much larger than the methyl group in toluene. As a consequence, the steric interference between the alkylating group and the existing *isopropyl* group within the *meta*-oriented carbonium ion intermediate (VI) will be much greater.

Thus, *para*-orientation in this case, in contrast to *meta*-condensation in the case of toluene, can be reasonably explained on the basis of the steric hindrance involved in the process (cf. Hennion, Driesch and Dee, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1102; Mukherji *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 19, 328).

The ketone (III) was reduced (Clemmensen) and the resulting tetralin derivative (IV) dehydrogenated with sulphur to 1-methyl-6-*isopropyl*naphthalene (V).

Similarly, cumene was acted upon with allylacetone in presence of aluminium chloride, when 5-(*p*-cumyl)-hexan-2-one (VII) was obtained in 40% yield. The assignment of the *para*-orientation in the above product (VII) was based on its hypiodite oxidation to the acid (II). The identity of the two samples of (II) was established by the melting points and mixed melting points of their *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivatives. The ketone (VII) was reduced with sodium and moist ether to the carbinol (VIII) which on cyclisation with H_2SO_4 (conc.) furnished the tetralin derivative (IX). Dehydrogenation of (IX) with sulphur afforded a good yield of 1:4-dimethyl-6-*isopropyl*naphthalene (X), previously synthesised by Ruzicka *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 140; 1936, 19, 370) by a much longer route.

p-Cymene was then studied under a similar sequence of reactions. When subjected to the Friedel-Crafts alkylation reaction with ethyl allylacetate under our standard condition, it gave ethyl 4-(2'-methyl-5'-*isopropyl*phenyl)-valerate (XI) in 58% yield.

The electrophilic attack at the 2-position of the *p*-cymene molecule is in agreement with the findings of the earlier workers (Le Fèvre, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 977, 980), although substitution should have taken place at the 3-position according to the accepted order of inductive effect of alkyl groups. This reverse order in the electrophilic attack has been ascribed by Ganguly and Le Fèvre (*ibid.*, 1934, 848, 852) to the steric repulsion due to the increasing size of the alkyl group (cf. Hennion, Driesch and Dee, *loc. cit.*). On the other hand, consideration of the well-known π -bond resonance (hyperconjugation) possibilities (Baker and Nathan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1844) suggests that the position *ortho* to the methyl group should be more susceptible to electrophilic attack, as found in the present work, than the position *ortho* to the isopropyl group.

The ester (XI) was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid (XII). The point of attachment of the valeric acid moiety was proved by an alternative synthesis of the acid (XII) according to the following scheme :

3-(*p*-Cymoyl-2')-propionic acid (XX) was prepared by reacting *p*-cymene with succinic anhydride in presence of aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene (Guha and Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 13). The keto-acid (XX) was esterified and the ester (XXI) acted upon with one molecular proportion of methylmagnesium iodide, when the unsaturated acid (XXII) and/or the corresponding γ -lactone (?) was obtained in 81% yield, which on reduction with red phosphorus and hydriodic acid furnished the acid (XII). The identity of the two samples of the acid (XII) was established by the m. p. and mixed m. p. of their *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivatives.

The acid (XII) was then cyclised, as described earlier, and the resulting tetralone (XIII) reduced (Clemmensen) and dehydrogenated with sulphur to obtain 1:8-dimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XV) in a good yield.

Similarly, *p*-cymene on reaction with allylacetone furnished 5-(2'-methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-hexan-2-one (XVI) in 44% yield. This ketone was oxidised by sodium hypiodite to the acid (XII), proving thereby that the Friedel-Crafts alkylation had taken place at a position *ortho* to the methyl group in *p*-cymene.

By following the same sequence of reactions with the ketone (XVI) as in the case of cumene series, namely, reduction (sodium and moist ether), cyclisation (sulphuric acid) and dehydrogenation (sulphur), 1:4:8-trimethyl-5-isopropyl-naphthalene (XIX) was obtained in a satisfactory overall yield.

E X P E R I M E N T A L *

(WITH N. K. MAHESHWARY)

Ethyl 4-(p-Cumyl)-valerate (I).—Cumene (75 c.c.) was subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction with ethyl allylacetate (25 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (52 g.), exactly according to the conditions laid down for the reaction with toluene (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1439). After working up in the usual way 32 g. (66%) of (I) was obtained, b.p. 160-62°/10 mm. (Found: C, 77.61; H, 9.53. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 77.37; H, 9.74%).

4-(p-Cumyl)-valeric Acid (II).—The ester (I: 16 g.) was hydrolysed with alcoholic KOH (10 g. in 10 c.c. water and 220 c.c. alcohol) by refluxing for 13 hours, and then the hydrolysate was worked up in the usual way to give 12 g. (84%) of the acid (II) as a colorless mobile liquid, b.p. 161-65°/15 mm. (Found: C, 75.94; H, 9.20. $C_{14}H_{20}O$ requires C, 76.32; H, 9.15%).

The *S-benzylisothiouronium* derivative was prepared in the usual manner (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longman, 1948, p. 738) and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 125°. (Found: N, 7.22. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 7.05%).

4-Methyl-7-isopropyl-1-tetralone (III).—The acid (II: 11.5 g.) was cyclised in the same manner as in the case of 4-(*m*-tolyl)-valeric acid (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1499), using 13.8 g. of PCl_5 , to yield 8 g. (76%) of the tetralone (III), b.p. 146-48°/20 mm., as a colorless oil. (Found: C, 83.34; H, 8.87. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{18}O$: C, 83.12; H, 8.97%).

The *semicarbazone* of (III) was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 175-76° (Ruzicka *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 176° decomp.). (Found: N, 16.60. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{21}ON_3$: N, 16.21%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m. p. 146-47°. (Found: N, 14.50. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.65%).

1-Methyl-6-isopropyltetralin (IV).—The ketone (III: 8 g.) was refluxed with amalgamated zinc (18 g.), HCl (conc., 30 c.c.), water (14 c.c.), toluene (25 c.c.) and acetic acid (1 c.c.) for 36 hours in an oil-bath at 120°-140°. After every six hours 5 c.c. of HCl was added. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and yielded 5.5 g. (74%) of the tetralin (IV), b.p. 154-56°/9 mm. (Found: C, 89.43; H, 10.43. $C_{14}H_{20}$ requires C, 89.29; H, 10.71%).

1-Methyl-6-isopropyl-naphthalene (V).—The tetralin derivative (IV: 5 g.) was heated with sulphur (2.1 g.) at 150° for about 6 hours and then steam-distilled. The distillate was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract cleared with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Fractionation gave 3.1 g. (66%) of the desired product (V), b. p. 117-20°/7 mm. (Found: C, 90.96; H, 8.92. $C_{14}H_{18}$ requires C, 91.25; H, 8.75%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from alcohol as orange needles, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 10.30. $C_{20}H_{19}O_7N_3$ requires N, 10.16%).

Oxidation of 4-(p-Cumyl)-valeric Acid (II).—The acid (II: 1 g.) was oxidised by alkaline permanganate* solution (prepared from 30 g. of $KMnO_4$, 600 c.c. water and 2

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

pellets of NaOH) by refluxing for 12 hours. The manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to a small bulk and then acidified, when 0.4 g. of terephthalic acid was obtained. The *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative of the acid was prepared in the usual manner, m. p. 202-203° (Vogel, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 204°).

5-(*p*-Cumyl)-hexan-2-one (VII).—Cumene (80 c.c.) was subjected to the $AlCl_3$ -catalysed reaction with allylacetone (20 g.) and $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 42 g.) exactly as in the case of (I), when 17 g. (40%) of the ketone (VII) was obtained, b. p. 145-48°/8 mm. (Found: C, 82.63; H, 10.00. $C_{15}H_{22}O$ requires C, 82.5; H, 10.16%).

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 81-82°. (Found: N, 15.12. $C_{15}H_{22}ON_3$ requires N, 15.27%).

5-(*p*-Cumyl) hexan-2-ol (VIII).—To a solution of the above ketone (VII: 14 g.) in moist ether (120 c.c.) were added gradually small pieces of sodium (20 g.). Whenever the reaction subsided 1-2 c.c. of water was added. After the whole amount of sodium had been consumed, the mixture was worked up in the usual way, when 9 g. (63%) of the alcohol (VIII) was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 160-63°/8 mm. (Found: C, 81.35; H, 10.74. $C_{15}H_{24}O$ requires C, 81.76; H, 10.98%).

1:4-Dimethyl-6-isopropyltetralin (IX).—The above carbinol (VIII) was treated in the cold with ice-cooled H_2SO_4 (10 c.c., *d* 1.84) which was added gradually with shaking for 20 minutes. The contents were allowed to attain the room temperature and then decomposed with ice and worked up in the usual manner, when the tetralin derivative (IX) was obtained in 71% yield (5.9 g.), b. p. 131-34°/10 mm. (Found: C, 89.00; H, 10.84. $C_{15}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.04; H, 10.96%).

1:4-Dimethyl-6-isopropyl-naphthalene (X).—The above tetralin (4 g.) was dehydrogenated with sulphur (1.6 g.) and worked up in the way as in the case of (IV), when 3 g. of 1:4-dimethyl-6-isopropyl-naphthalene (X) was obtained, b.p. 136-37°/9 mm. (Found: C, 90.45; H, 8.96. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{18}$: C, 90.85; H, 9.15%).

The picrate was prepared by the usual method and was crystallised from ethanol as deep yellow needles, m. p. 102-103° (Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 140; 1936, 19, 370, report m. p. 103°). (Found: N, 10.10. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{21}O_7N_3$: N, 9.83%).

Oxidation of 5-(*p*-Cumyl)-hexan-2-one with Sodium Hypoiodite.—The ketone (VII: 3 g.) was dissolved in dioxane (60 c.c.) and 10% NaOH solution (80 c.c.). The mixture was well stirred and some iodine solution (prepared in the ratio of KI:I:H₂O = 2:1:4) was added when a yellow colour developed. The addition of iodine solution was continued till the dark red colour of iodine persisted in the cold as well as on warming on the water-bath (60°) for 2 to 3 minutes. The excess of iodine was removed by adding a few drops of dilute NaOH solution. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand when iodoform separated at the bottom. The aqueous layer was decanted and extracted with ether to remove any unchanged ketone. The aqueous layer was acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the liberated iodine colour discharged with sodium thiosulphate solution. The oily organic layer was taken up in ether, washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent the residue gave on distillation under reduced pressure 1.65 g. of the acid (II), b. p. 158-60°/5 mm.

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 124-25°, undepressed when mixed with the corresponding derivative, previously prepared from (II).

(WITH SARJIT SINGH SANDHU)

Ethyl 4-(2'-Methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-valerate (XI).—*p*-Cymene (100 c.c.) was subjected to the cationoid reaction with ethyl allylacetate (15 g.) and anhydrous AlCl_3 (30 g.), following exactly the conditions laid down for (I), and the reaction mixture of being worked up in the same manner yielded 18 g. (58%) of the ester (XI), b. p. 145-46°/8 mm. (Found: C, 77.43; H, 10.12. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.82; H, 9.99%).

4-(2'-Methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-valeric Acid (XII).—The above ester (18 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic KOH solution (2 g. in 5 c.c. water and 200 c.c. ethanol) for about 12 hours. After working up in the usual way the acid (XII) was obtained as a colorless oil, b. p. 172-74°/5 mm. in 81% yield (13 g.). (Found: C, 76.52; H, 9.23. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46%).

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative was prepared in the standard manner (Vogel, *loc. cit.*) and was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 119°. (Found: N, 7.10. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 7.03%).

4:5-Dimethyl-8-isopropyl-1-tetralone (XIII).—The above acid (XII: 10 g.) was converted into its acid chloride with PCl_5 (10 g.) and then cyclised with AlCl_3 (6.3 g., anhyd.) in the same manner as for (II), when 7 g. (76%) of the ketone (XIII) was obtained; b. p. 128-30°/6 mm. (Found: C, 83.00; H, 9.45. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 83.28; H, 10.96%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and was crystallised as red needles from ethyl acetate, m. p. 220-21°. (Found: N, 14.30. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.14%).

1:8-Dimethyl-5-isopropyltetralin (XIV).—The ketone (XIII: 7 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of amalgamated zinc (45 g.), HCl (conc., 70 c.c.), toluene (40 c.c.), acetic acid (2 c.c.) and water (34 c.c.) for 34 hours at 120°-140°. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way when 5.3 g. (81%) of the tetralin (XIV) was obtained, b. p. 118-21°/10 mm. (Found: C, 89.10; H, 10.82. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}$ requires C, 89.00; H, 10.96%).

1:8-Dimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XV).—The tetralin (XIV: 5 g.) was heated with sulphur (12 g.) at 180° for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was then worked up in the same way as for (V), when 2.8 g. (57%) of the desired product (XV) was obtained, b. p. 125-28°/6 mm. (Found: C, 90.74; H, 8.86. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}$ requires C, 90.85; H, 9.15%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised as deep yellow needles from ethanol, m. p. 146°. (Found: N, 9.68. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires N, 9.83%).

Ethyl 3-(p-Cymoyl-2')-propionate (XXI).—3-(*p*-Cymoyl-2')-propionic acid (50 g.), obtained by the procedure of Dev and Guha (*loc. cit.*), was refluxed for 12 hours with absolute alcohol (550 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 34 c.c.). The mixture was then worked up in the usual manner when 44 g. of the above ester was obtained, b. p. 190-92°/12 mm. (Found: C, 72.96; H, 8.28. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.28; H, 8.40%).

4-Methyl-4-(2'-methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-vinylacetic Acid (XXII).—To the above ester (15 g.) in dry ether (200 c.c.) was slowly added methylmagnesium iodide (prepared from 9 g. of MeI, 1.5 g. of Mg and 100 c.c. of dry ether) with shaking and ice-cooling. After standing overnight the reaction mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours and was then decomposed with iced HCl, and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was shaken with four portions of dilute NaOH solution. The combined NaOH extract was heated with norit, filtered and acidified with iced HCl (dil.), and the liberated oil was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution dried and the solvent removed, when 10 g. (81%) of the unsaturated acid was obtained. This acid was unsaturated to bromine in chloroform (cf. Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, 28, 69). The crude acid was directly treated for reduction without purification.

4-(2'-Methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-valeric Acid (XII).—The above unsaturated acid (10 g.) was refluxed with red phosphorus (7 g.) and HI (80 g., *d* 1.7) in an oil-bath at 130°-140° for 15 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and then with 5% Na₂CO₃ solution. The alkaline washings were acidified and the liberated oil taken up in ether and dried (Na₂SO₄). On removal of the solvent the residue after distillation afforded 6 g. of a colorless oil, b.p. 166-68°/5 mm., showing no unsaturation to bromine in chloroform. (Found: C, 76.63; N, 9.18. C₁₅H₂₂O₂ requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46%).

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative of the above sample was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 119°, undepressed on admixture with the corresponding derivative of the acid (XII).

5-(2'-Methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-hexan-2-one (XVI).—*p*-Cymene (60 c.c.) was condensed with allylacetone (16 g.) in presence of AlCl₃ (32 g.), following exactly the conditions described in the preparation of (I), when 19 g. (43%) of the ketone (XVI) was obtained, coming over at 155-58°/9 mm. (Found: C, 82.58; H, 10.52. C₁₈H₂₄O requires C, 82.70; H, 10.41%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 156°. (Found: N, 14.60. C₁₇H₂₇ON₃ requires N, 14.53%).

5-(2'-Methyl-5'-isopropylphenyl)-hexan-2-ol (XVII).—The above ketone (XVI: 14 g.) was reduced with sodium (11 g.) and moist ether according to the procedure described earlier. The reduced product was worked up when 11 g. of the carbinol (XVII) was obtained, b.p. 138-42°/5 mm. (Found: C, 81.73; H, 11.23. C₁₈H₂₆O requires C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

1:4:8-Trimethyl-5-isopropyltetralin (XVIII).—The above carbinol (9 g.) was cyclised with H₂SO₄ (*d* 1.84, 9 c.c.) in the same way as for (VII), when 6 g. of the tetralin (XVIII) was obtained, b.p. 110-14°/4 mm. (Found: C, 89.03; H, 11.24. C₁₈H₂₄ requires C, 88.82; H, 11.18%).

1:4:8-Trimethyl-5-isopropyl-naphthalene (XIX).—Dehydrogenation of (XVIII: 5 g.) with sulphur (1.7 g.) was effected under the conditions described in the case of (IX), and on similar working up, the reaction mixture gave 3.2 g. of the desired product (XIX), b.p. 130-33°/8 mm. (Found: C, 90.43; H, 9.43. C₁₈H₂₀ requires C, 90.50; H, 9.52%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised as red plates from alcohol, m. p. 114°. (Found : N, 9.25. $C_{22}H_{23}O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.50%).

Oxidation of the Ketone (XVI) with Sodium Hypoiodite.—The ketone (XVI : 3.5 g.) was oxidised with sodium hypoiodite solution in the same way as described for the ketone (VII). After working up in the same manner, 1.9 g. of the acid (XII), b.p. 172-75°/6 mm., was obtained. The *S-benzylisothouronium* derivative of the above acid was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 119° (undepressed on admixture with the sample obtained earlier from the acid, XII).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
HOSHIARPUR,

Received May 10, 1956.

FRIEDEL-CRAFTS' REACTION INVOLVING UNSATURATED KETONES AND ESTERS. PART VI. ALKYLATION OF ANISOL WITH ETHYL ALLYLACETATE AND ALLYLACETONE

By S. M. MUKHERJI, O. P. VIG, AND N. K. MAHESHWARY

Cationoid reaction of ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone with anisol has been studied. Of particular interest is the facile cyclodehydration undergone by the condensation product of anisol with allylacetone. Also, the Friedel-Crafts alkylation products proved to be readily accessible intermediates in convenient syntheses of several methoxynaphthalene homologues.

In earlier communications (Mukherji *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1202; 1953, 18, 1499; 1954, 19, 328; this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 697; 1956, 33, 1), Friedel-Crafts' alkylation of aromatic substrates with ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone was shown to initiate convenient synthetic routes to the different types of polynuclear hydrocarbons. It has now been decided to extend the scope of this method to alkyl aryl ethers. The Friedel-Crafts alkylation of anisol is rather well known (Price, "Organic Reaction", John Wiley, 1949, 3, 65) and the *para*-orientated products are the preponderant components, although in the case of reaction with *cyclohexene* (Bodroux, *Ann. chim.*, 1929, x, 11, 511) the *ortho*-isomer is reported to be in greater proportion.

However, when anisol was subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction at 0°-5° with ethyl allylacetate, 4-(*p*-anisyl)-valerate (I) was the exclusive product obtained in 31% yield. On hydrolysis (I) gave a quantitative yield of the acid (II). That the product (I) was *para*-orientated was proved by alkaline permanganate oxidation of the